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for Systems Biology
Europe

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Draft Proposal on Connections

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Introduction

An infrastructure is a network of objects and facilities that enables a certain purpose. A metro network's stations, rail tracks, signals, personnel etc. together serve customers – and through them their companies – to go from A to B, for instance to enable them to engage in economic activities, whilst they live elsewhere. Correspondingly, the ISBE infrastructure consists as much of the stations (nodes) as of the connections (tracks). Because systems biology is all about an integration of research and development activities, the connections and the synergies that they bring about are crucial. The R&D activities are too extensive and diverse to be attained by individual research groups or even research centres.

ISBE connections should be formatted in ways that maximize the usefulness of the centres and, thereby, the infrastructure as a whole. They should greatly increase the yield and efficiency of European science and technology by enabling them to embrace systems approaches.

The ISBE WP13 aims to develop recommendations for what the connections in the infrastructure should comprise and how they should be structured in order to best serve the above purpose. WP13 is in the process of defining interfaces at ISBE nodes that enable R&D activities to integrate seamlessly. Connections include computer-only, computer-assisted and human-human interactions. WP13 will also define ways in which large systems biology tasks can be optimally partitioned over activities that can best be accomplished at ISBE nodes, whilst enabling optimal continuous integration through the connections. Through ISBE, large systems biology-driven community efforts become feasible by connecting the expertise and resources of multiple different projects in past and present. This builds ISBE as a platform from which to launch large-scale integrative visionary projects with great scientific and societal impact.

Background information to WP13

Objectives of WP13

ISBE will consist of nodes and strong connections between these. Particularly Systems Biology needs to integrate various types of expertise that do not exist at a single location at the highest level of excellence. WP13 has the aim to make these connections seamless, ultrafast and user friendly. More specifically the objectives are:

- to define and design all possible connections between ISBE nodes that will promote European Systems Biology
- to design standard interfaces at ISBE nodes that enable computer assisted connecting
- to design ways in which large systems biology tasks can be partitioned over nodes and the results reintegrated

Relationship to other work packages

WP3 (Overall Infrastructure, Eligibility and Accessibility) will define the nodes and WP13 (Connections) will define the edges of the ISBE network. Together with WP4 (Data Generation), WP13 will define the technical interfaces for the connections into and out of the data generation centres. WP13 will design the technical aspects of interfacing/data exchange during systems biology research projects (e.g. web services); WP5 (Community Building and Synergies) will define how the various organisations involved engage with each other before, and after, the active research happens. The insights gained by WP13 on the best ways of communicating, will serve WP7 (Strategy Vision and Advocacy) in developing further vision. WP11 (Funding, Governance and Legal) will mediate the discussions of how to implement the best ways of connecting research into actually funded research projects of research consortia. WP15 (Innovation, Impact and Exploitation) will explore possible connections with industry, where WP13 focuses on connections within ISBE and between ISBE and academic institutions.

Vision and implications for the connections

A systems biology research program consists of various components that need to be integrated almost continuously. These components deal with the creation of mathematical models, the comparison with models already existing in literature, the finding of parameter values in literature, the model-driven design of new experiments, the fine-tuning of the experimental approach to appropriate standards (e.g. carrying out the experiment at physiological pH and temperature), the identification of the best standard experimental model system, the execution of experiments, the analysis of the acquired data, the integration of results into an improved version of the model, consistency checks with consensus scientific knowledge, model analysis to discover biological principles, model interrogation for testable predictions, and model deployment in the context of medicine, pharmacology, and biotechnology.

At present, researchers engaging with systems biology are typically constrained to organize all these activities in their own labs, or to write research proposals for collaborations with other groups that they predefine to contribute lacking components. The former strategy often gives rise to suboptimal quality in many of the components. The latter strategy greatly slows down the progress of systems biology research. The ISBE connections aim to solve this problem. They will provide individual research groups with the possibility to efficiently hook up to systems biology centres (the ISBE core) that make state-of-the-art systems biology expertise available. Connections with the ISBE core should be seamless, providing rapid access such to requested systems biology components, and in real time whenever possible. Systems biology expertise in the core will be of high and certified quality. Because systems biology is not the simple addition of modelling, experimentation, data mining, etc., yet a synergy between such activities, the ISBE core comprises of a network of systems biology expertise centres that is organized to operate as a dynamic, flexible and scalable infrastructure.

This vision requires two types of scientific connections. First, a set of live and continuous connections between the core systems biology centres (the ISBE nodes). The connections should effectively enable a single expertise centre that may in fact consist of component centres that are geographically distributed throughout Europe. To ISBE users this should enable the provision of a single point of entry into the infrastructure. The second type of connection is that between research groups wishing to engage with systems biology, and the ISBE core. This should enable workflows that resemble task processing in complex computations, where separate threads for a specific job are carried out on different cores, wherever possible in parallel, and controlled by proficient instruction sets.

Research groups or consortia that engage with ISBE will remain the dominant components of the research project, contributing their own expertise and directing the research programme. ISBE will assist in directing the research projects by supplying the expertise that helps ensure the systems biology is of high and certified quality, integrating all that is required to understand the biological question at hand (e.g. modelling, experimental design, connections with systems theory, use of valid experimental data, etc.).

Specifications of the connections

1. Interconnecting the core centres to become a single ISBE core

The connections between the core centres should be such that researchers in the various core centres can seamlessly collaborate, ideally instantaneously. This may involve broadband connections, video connections, cloud services etc. to link up experimenters and/or modellers in real time. Equipment will therefore require clear standards to create uniform input and output allowing for the normalization of machine-machine interactions.

At the human level, it requires people that work the ISBE core to be very open to communication, to not be competitive at the individual level but rather at the ISBE level, and to be both highly trained in their own (inter-)discipline as well as trained in trans-disciplinary fashion, to readily understand sufficient of other disciplines to be able to communicate effectively.

Overall, ISBE connections should be formatted in ways that maximize the usefulness of the centres and, thereby, infrastructure as a whole. At the scientific level, the infrastructure aims at efficiently supporting and delivering systems biology workflows. Therefore the connections among nodes and centres should empower workflows that are i) model-driven, and ii) integration-centric.

2. Connecting a user (e.g. research group) to the ISBE core

The following considerations have been recognized or proposed as consequential and require assessment and scrutiny by experts and the systems biology community at large.

- As much as possible provide a single point of entry/exit to ISBE. Users should not have to search around.
- Connections include computer-only, computer-assisted and human-human interactions.
- ISBE will offer a systems-based approach integrating multiple activities (e.g. modelling, transcriptome, proteome and data mining). By default, a modelling-driven research strategy will be used, where “model” may refer to, for instance, a complex set of differential equations or to a self-consistent depiction of a network, i.e. to any formalization. If the client wishes to forego this offer, e.g. because they avail of all required SB activities including the integration, this will be accommodated.
- Depending on the requested expertise, user connections and interactions can be of various types. These are being assessed for the various activities that ISBE should support, drawing from experiences in other projects and consortia.
 - **Local modalities**
 - Physically go to a core centre to do the research oneself
 - Mobile experts – an expert in the ISBE core comes to the research group
 - **Remote modalities**
 - Sending samples to ISBE core centres for analysis
 - Remote modelling through ISBE-net, e.g. accessing and going from existing models or model-ready datasets; whenever possible using automated workflows
 - Remote research (project) planning (e.g. involving multiple expertise, and thus multiple nodes/centres, sometimes simultaneously)
 - Remote training, e.g. online experimental instruction or modelling teaching
 - Remote experimentation in ISBE core centres (e.g. through web interfaces)

*N.B. The ways in which one can interact with a specific expertise is highly dependent on i) the types of personnel that ISBE will support for it (e.g. paid as-a-service vs. scientific stakeholder), ii) the extent to which an expertise centre is distributed over different labs and countries, iii) the overall accessibility level of the required expertise (e.g. labour-intensive vs. technology-driven services; open vs. more restricted resources). These interactions will be explored through ***persona modelling** with the help of experts to reach Deliverable 13.3. Outcomes will optimise both nodes and connections.*

3. Interfaces: connections and nodes

When defining interfaces to couple the scientific activities within ISBE, various notions and recommendations have been delineated:

- As much as possible provide a single point of entry/exit to ISBE. Users should not have to search around (Figure 1) and it is the strategic aim of ISBE to use the present and past research outcomes into improved models as the basis for serving new ISBE users.
- As much as possible reflect the modelling-driven identity of ISBE, i.e. driven by integration through formal representation that is computable in some way (i.e. unambiguous and predictive) (Figure 1).
- As much as possible make services available through web services and rapid internal communication (with human supervision where required, eventually working towards more automation in many processes)
- Build on existing (high-speed) connections (including other ESFRI)
- Real-time requirements will be different for different services (data speed)
- Connections will be different depending on secure vs. non-secure access requirements (secure connectivity, local storage, access control etc.)

MICs play a central role in judging, planning and managing the research activities of ISBE, as they have the expertise to ensure the highest quality of the systems biology approaches that ISBE implements in the research projects of its users. MICs operate in terms of full model integration and thereby monitor the progress of research projects. Compliant to the systems biology approach, the MICs use a core model (in the sense of an unambiguous formal and computable representation of proposed reality) to drive integration. Data are relevant if they are linkable to components of the core model. This is the same for components models, tools that have been or can be used to analyse the data, and the maps that define the system being analysed as part of the full biological entity.

Several steps are foreseen in which MICs steer the ISBE projects: (i) formulate, maintain and develop the core model, (ii) access ISBE infrastructure, (iii) develop the integrated research plan (including financial and legal issues) involving one or more ISBE centres and other contributors, (iv) monitor and manage the research progress, (v) finalize and scientifically report on the project, and (vi) deposit the project outcomes - models, data, maps, or tools - in the repositories for use in future projects. MICs report on the specific project they are engaged in to the user that initiated the project. They also report a resume of their activities regularly to a central ISBE office.

Based on the types of research project or its needs, projects can generate four general types of results and outcomes: models, data, maps, and tools. All these should be assessed and annotated in Stewardship Centres (SCs) for reusability in subsequent research projects. Tools can be technologies developed in all different centres, for instance: modelling tools or algorithms (developed in MICs), imaging tools (in DGCs), automated annotation applications (in SCs), etc. The stewardship of tools is crucial to make available, for example, state-of-the-art raw image pre-processing for a specific type of microscopy to all ISBE DGCs that need to perform that.

Consensus physiological maps can be outcomes of research project in the MICs, or may come from special projects that specifically aim to construct integrated maps for specific organisms.

With increasing size and complexity of projects or programmes, and for the development of the integration of partial models to models of entire organisms, special MICs may need to become involved.

Figure 1 – The model-driven and integration-centric modus operandi of ISBE centres. A research question/project brought in by users launches the formation of an integrated research plan by the Integration section of the Modelling and Integration Centre (MIC), involving all relevant centres. After consensus, research activities are steered – and project progress is ensured – by the on-going integration activity of the MIC, through assimilating data, models, maps and tools involving all associated centres. Stewardship Centres (SC) ensure standards, ontologies, quality and annotation compliance of relevant data identified, and keeps parameterised models and their data for future use.

Dashed arrows: request. Solid arrow: data or model flow. Users can also contribute data and models, which is not indicated in the diagram.

4. Modularization

For the modularization of scientific activities within ISBE, various notions and recommendations have been delineated:

- Part of the remit of the MICs is the improvement of the systems-biology research strategies entertained by ISBE. An important aspect of this is the issue of how to organize a systems biology program/question such that it can be optimally mapped onto ISBE core centres, which all have their own expertise.

- Modularization of systems biology into subtasks that can be allocated to specific centres in the core – for parallel processing and subsequent reintegration – will be important to define those centres.
- Modelling expertise is an integrated part of the infrastructure through shared resources. Different types of modelling expertise (e.g. stochastic vs. Bayesian vs. ODE-based modelling) that exist in various core centres should help define the modularization (Figure 2).
- A specific strategy of modularization may use the traditional pathway identification, as prevalent in cell biology. One centre may then focus on glycolysis, a second on the MAP kinase pathway, a third on heart contraction, a fourth on liver zonation. The corresponding different models could be run in interaction after the corresponding interfaces have been defined (e.g. MAP kinase for signalling, glycolysis for the required ATP and gene expression in between), where interface definition is a task of the SCs with input from the MICs.

*The aspects related to modularization proposed here should be tested through ****scenario modelling** with the help of experts to reach Deliverable 13.3. The definitions of nodes and connections should also be improved using the results of the scenario modelling.*

***Personas** to scrutinise (not definitive):

- SB expert PhD student/PDRA working on systems problem
- Idem, but non-expert in SB
- Stakeholder from industry (define with WP15)
- Node manager (that now also needs to provide service)
- PI in research group that wants to use ISBE
- Scientist in core node
- Governance persona (quality control / compliance etc.)
- Non-SB end user (e.g. clinician)
- Funding persona

****Scenarios** to scrutinise (not definitive):

- Predicting biomarkers upon drug administration to a mouse and validating this experimentally.
- Develop a personalized therapy for an inborn error of metabolism based on Recon2 map.
- Engineer a yeast cell to robustly produce octanol

- Once more extensive models have been made and parameterized, mathematical tools (such as elementary mode analysis) can be implemented to seek better definitions of modules than can be distributed over different centres for systems biology. This may then define new centres, perhaps that combine all carbon and energy metabolism or all nuclear hormone signalling, and a more efficient organization.
- After defining what centres/nodes can do individually, we should define how a node should be able to ask another node to perform a demarcated and recognizable job; this extends the definitions of the connections described above.
- Design of experiments and of the modelling to be done in DGCs and MCs will be coordinated by MICs and involve the relevant SCs to supply relevant pre-existing models, data, maps and tools.
- The SCs define the organization of data such that different modelling methods can accept them (Figure 2) and ensure resource “translatability”.
- Organize modelling methods such that they all use the same (or corresponding) data (Figure 2), to avoid different models of the same system using different, inconsistent or incomparable datasets to describe said system.
- The ISBE SCs select from existing data or models (e.g. present in Elixir repositories) those that are relevant to solve systems biology problems (e.g. through pointers).
- The stewardship of models should enable the quick redeployment of existing answers or solutions by running the models (e.g. through JWS-online).
- When defining the services to be performed in ISBE (e.g. for biochemical characterization, cellular characterization, etc.) we should draw from existing successes (e.g. EUCOMM mouse mutant and high-resolution phenotyping consortium. EUCOMM also has experience with issues at the level of ownership within distributed workflows).
- ISBE will set up a growth model: from mere human input/expertise through many iterations to an infrastructure where the interactions are more automated (computer workflows communicating through web services; robot scientists assisting).
- Specify (a suite of) systems biology driven dynamic-integration workflows that can integrate the results from smaller parts of a research program, or from diverse research projects, enabling predictions for the whole program
- ISBE should consider using and/or extending MCISB workflows (liaising with WP2)

Figure 2 – The ISBE infrastructure will operate such that modelling expertise becomes an integrated and accessible part of the infrastructure through shared resources (nodes in green; connections in blue). The ISBE is self-reinforcing in that the outputs are annotated, versioned, standardized results of known quality, which can find their place in the same federate storage layout for subsequent iterations or projects, or even further integrated into large systems biology efforts for virtualization of large biological entities (like cells, organs, or full organisms).

5. Standardization, automation

For the standardization and automation requirements to support ISBE workflows, various notions and recommendations have been delineated:

- ISBE should draw from EBI and MCISB (both have formalized the process of standards development and implementation). Standards should only be implemented when necessary. Pilot experiments may forego precise standards, but for every finalized experiment and dataset, replicas should be made using ISBE-certified SOPs.
- Different classes of standards need to be accommodated: 1) standards of outputs of ISBE (data, models etc.); 2) standards of processes (i.e. a combination of human activities and ways to access tools and resources; 3) standards for procedures that experimenters adhere to in laboratory settings.
- Standardization should be done such that it anticipates that standards will have to be updated periodically (versioned standards). Standards will have to be dynamic.
- ISBE should drive supporting standards if the smaller communities (like SBML) would not actively or continuously support them.
- The standardization should include that of the inputs and outputs of ISBE activities, such that they can be integrated with other modules that have already been defined by systems biology, e.g. through ISBE. This should be done with potential automated integration in mind. This requires standards and systematic, fit-for-purpose data annotations. It will be facilitated by having the model organised to follow the structure and function of the biological entity it describes.
- For model standardization (but also for user interfaces), ISBE should draw from the COMBINE initiative, and from JWS-online and BioModels experiences.
- The model standards should follow the Minimal Requirements strategy (e.g. MIAMI), i.e. to define the minimal requirements to run (early on) in ISBE and the minimal required performance.
- Many key aspects of models can only be found by interrogating them correctly or doing experiments on them. Some functional curating activity may need to be considered, including for instance sanity checks of model performance after having adapted it.
- Standardization of biological experiments. The definition of SOPs should draw amply from the developments in SysMO and MCISB. Quality control and quality rating procedures should be developed as well (e.g. reporting on the reproducibility between different laboratories) (liaising with WP2).
- DGCs should be able to provide standardized outputs with evidence of reproducibility also in different laboratories of the same DGC.
- When developing the above, ISBE should draw from Biosharing (liaising with WP2).

6. Quality control

Various notions and recommendations have been outlined with respect to quality control:

- Delineate quality issues from the distribution of tasks.
- Quality control will be linked to task distribution by making a specific group of people (the corresponding node) responsible for a manageable well-defined subset of data to guarantee and annotate data quality and indeed for the quality of their task, with another centre serving as reviewer.
- Quality control of data differs from quality control of models, where this activity for models is highly innovative.

- ISBE will need to enforce quality assessment, enforcement and compliance, because the products delivered by ISBE users will depend on a number of ISBE activities that should all be of sufficient quality in order to make the overall result robust. The MICs should implement methodologies such as global sensitivity analysis to help assess the quality/robustness of the outputs of systems biology activities that use ISBE.
- A (federated) method for the selection, dispatch and tracking of tasks, optimized for federate storage layout (as in above; e.g. middleware layers, used in by VPH, VLN, EBI) should be implemented and/or developed, and optimized. This will include versioning, data stamping of activities, storage of data and workflows.
- A system should be developed where data stored/associated with models are annotated by identifiers of their quality, reproducibility, appropriateness (e.g. correct pH). This should be done such that, by e.g. using sensitivity analysis, the model can compute the estimated quality of its conclusions.
- Quality control methodology for data management should be implemented and developed (liaise with WP2 and draw from activities by Wolfgang Müller).

7. Integrating different projects into large systems biology programmes

The ISBE infrastructure is to be used by multiple systems biology programmes that study various biological systems. Every now and then, projects can be launched run that study adjacent parts of the same system or the same parts but from a different angle. ISBE will store the corresponding models, with parameters associated and data sources etc. linked. The models will have standardized interfaces such that they can immediately be linked together. This enables ISBE to serve large systems biology programmes that aim to develop the systems biology of an organ, an ecosystem, or an organism (e.g. the digital yeast cell, the digital human). The ever growing association of partial models will already earlier be useful for other research programs that use ISBE, like the pharmaceutical industry seeking to use a whole-body, molecules-based model on glutathione-mediated drug detoxification as a function of genome sequence, lifestyle, and intended medicine dosage.

The intention of redeploying results in wider future contexts implies that users of ISBE will be asked to agree to have their data available to reinforce the infrastructure. Users that do not wish to do this may, for example, have to pay additional ISBE user fees.

8. External scientific connections

Together with other work packages – notably WP1, WP2, WP3, WP5, WP11 and WP15 – ISBE partners are actively engaging at multiple levels with external stakeholders. These interactions are on-going and include (but are not limited to):

- Non-systems biology stakeholders
 - o Other scientific experts (physicists, mathematicians, engineers)
 - o Medical researchers
 - o Non-expert connections, such historians, sociologists and philosophers of science, policy science
- Industry (liaising with WP15)
 - o Potential areas to liaise in pre-competitive modes (for instance software and hardware support)
 - o IP issues in systems biology collaborations (hidden connections?)

- to large national and European programmes (liaising with WP11)
 - HBP, IMI, JPIs, as well as large national initiatives (e.g. Virtual Liver Network)
 - Considering how existing centres under different conditions and different countries can link to ISBE business models in-the-making.
 - Consider positioning ISBE as the one-stop entity for (biomolecular) modelling programs.
 - SysMO, ERASysBio, other FP7, BBSRC; list expanding
 - Liaise with BioMedBridges (engaging with WP1)
 - To large non-European programmes (engaging with WP11)
 - VPH, EMBnet, American programmes, HD-Physiology; list expanding

Draft recommendations for the organisation and structure of ISBE nodes and centres

By connecting the expertise and resources of multiple different projects in past and present, ISBE should enable large systems biology-driven community efforts. This requires the ISBE centres to be conceived as part of an interconnected platform from which to launch integrative visionary projects with great scientific and societal impact, as well as the smaller projects that make important sub-models and resolve systems biology issues.

- Because systems biology is not the mere addition of modelling, experimentation, data mining, etc., yet a synergy between such activities, the ISBE core should be a network of systems biology expertise centres that is organized to operate as a dynamic, flexible and scalable infrastructure (enabling integration).
- DGCs and SC centres provide data generation and data stewardship in a model-driven fashion (Figure 1). This is different from ELIXIR. Data generation is tailored to the biological question at hand, e.g. under the relevant conditions, following dynamic biological structure, etc. Data stewardship deals with model-ready data. Therefore DGCs and SCs go beyond standard and reference datasets (like in ELIXIR) to supply project- and model-tailored data.
- In addition to modelling expertise, MCs harbour a separate central integration activity (Figure 1). This integrates SB research projects and links new project outcomes to a core model from which subsequent endeavours can draw. Modelling nodes are connected through integration
- Three types of scientific connections (N.B. “node” is used here to refer to an entity at a single geographic location; “centre” an entity corresponding to a single expertise, possibly distributed over different locations. Decide on consequent terminology):
 - A set of connections between core systems biology nodes of a certain type (e.g. the DGC nodes), effectively enabling a single expertise centre that may in fact consist of component nodes that are geographically distributed throughout Europe (providing a single point of entry into the infrastructure for users).
 - Connections between systems biology centres of different types (e.g. DGCs and MCs centres) enabling their integration when addressing a certain systems biology problem contributed by a user
 - Connections between research groups wishing to engage with systems biology, and the ISBE core. This should enable workflows that resemble task processing in complex computations, where separate threads for a specific job are carried out on different cores, wherever possible in parallel, and controlled by proficient instruction sets.
- At the machine level, equipment will require clear standards to create uniform input and output allowing for the normalization of machine-machine interactions.

- At the human level, it requires people that work the ISBE core to be very open to communication, to not be competitive at the individual level but rather at the ISBE level, and to be both highly trained in their own (inter-)discipline as well as trained in trans-disciplinary fashion.
- Workflows should have proficient means to monitor and manage the research progress
- Users should be asked to deposit the project outcomes - models, data, maps, or tools - in the repositories for use in future projects. Centres will have to find way to deal with users that do not wish to do so (e.g. additional ISBE user fees)
- Centres should support modularization of the systems biology question into subtasks that can be allocated to specific centres in the core – for parallel processing and subsequent reintegration. This will be important to define those centres.
 - Example: a specific strategy of modularization may use the traditional pathway identification, as prevalent in cell biology. One centre could focus on glycolysis, a second on the MAP kinase pathway, a third on heart contraction, a fourth on liver zonation. The corresponding different models could be run in interaction after the corresponding interfaces have been defined (e.g. MAP kinase for signalling, glycolysis for the required ATP and gene expression in between), where interface definition is a task of the SCs with input from the MCs.
- ISBE centres should support a growth model: from mere human input/expertise through much iteration to an infrastructure where the interactions are more automated
 - e.g. (a suite of) systems biology driven dynamic-integration workflows that can integrate the results from smaller parts of a research program, or from diverse research projects, enabling predictions for the whole program
- In addition to standardization and automation challenges, quality control issues should be considered (specifically by the SCs).